

Effect of International Financial Reporting Standard on the Quality of Financial Statement of Sterling Bank Plc.

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Abstract

The demand for reliable financial reporting is unavoidable for users who need it for investment and other decision-making purposes. Hence, this study examined the effect of International financial reporting standard on the quality of financial statement of Sterling Bank Plc. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population is represented by 150 members of staff of Sterling Bank in Ibadan, Oyo State. Sixty (60) staff were randomly selected, and questionnaire were administered to them. The study employed descriptive statistical method as well as the Statistical analysis for Social Sciences (SPSS) to analyze data. The result shows that there is a significant relationship between IFRS adoption and the clarity principle of Nigerian banks. There is need for essential qualities of information in financial reports. When annual reports are well organized users can comprehend what their needs are. Given the foregoing, the study recommended that companies should endeavour to use the opportunity presented by the adoption of IFRS to improve their business process and procedures, Nigeria's adoption of IFRS should be supported as a matter of urgency to enable full attainment of the country's economic potential, IFRS should be included in the syllabus of Accounting Department in the tertiary institutions so that students will have the knowledge before entering into the labour market and the accountancy institutes in Nigeria must embark on massive education training and retraining of their members through continuing professional development programmes.

Keywords: Financial reporting, Financial statement, IFRS, Sterling Bank.

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Introduction

The demand for reliable financial reporting is unavoidable for users who need it for investment and other decision-making purposes. Financial reports are only valuable if they represent an organization's "economic content" in terms of relevance, reliability, comparability, understandability, and timeliness. Standard makes accounting numbers comprehensible. Most nations had their own standards prior to the introduction of the IFRS, with local authorities in charge of creating and issuing them, even if some of them generally aligned with the IAS (Hao, Sun & Yin, 2019). In this vein, the Nigerian Accounting Standards Board (NASB) was responsible for developing and issuing Statements of Accounting Standards (SAS), and the Financial Reporting Council (FRC) of Nigeria was renamed as the regulatory body overseeing the adoption and implementation of IFRS in the new dispensation (Key & Kim, 2020).

As a result of increased globalization and increased competition, it is becoming increasingly important for countries and businesses to solve challenges that will make them more appealing to investors' capital, much like the proverbial beautiful bride. One of the undeniable benefits of adopting global accounting standards is increased access to cash from both local and international investors, among other things. And, as proponents of IFRS argue, organizations must embrace this set of accounting standards in order to take advantage of this benefit (Pena & Franco, 2017).

In Nigeria, the government has taken its stand to involve all stake holders including institutions before it finally decided to adopt the IFRS on a gradual basis. IFRS for SMEs is to be mandatorily adopted as of January 1, 2014. This means that all Small and Medium-sized Entities in Nigeria have been statutorily required to issue IFRS based financial statements for the year ended December 31, 2014.

The International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) are a new set of accounting standards that have been developed through a rigorous due diligence process and are now used in over 120 countries around the world, including Australia, Brazil, Canada, the European Union, South Africa, Nigeria, and many others (Hail, Tahou & Wang, 2017). The goal of financial reporting, according to accounting theory, is to eliminate information asymmetry between corporate management and parties contracting with their organization, and financial reporting does so by revealing relevant and timely information. International accounting systems provide an intriguing context to analyze the economic ramifications of financial reporting because there is considerable variance in accounting quality and economic efficiency across countries. The comparison of pre-changeover Nigeria GAAP (NGAAP) to IFRS and the identification of differences between the two

regimes is an important issue for users of financial statements (Hope, Thomas & Vyas, 2017).

The adoption of IFRS has been argued in contemporary literature to offer numerous financial and non-financial benefits. It is therefore in this connection that (and their predecessor IAS) constrain managerial discretion while submitted that IFRS impose a more comprehensive and highly detailed set of disclosure requirements than domestic accounting standards. When disclosure is improved upon and managerial discretions, with respect to treatment of accounting transactions, are constrained, this arguably suggests that IFRS will improve accounting quality and engender better financial reporting practices. Importantly, improved comparability is also one of the value-adding characteristics of IFRS as contended by its advocates.

However, the purpose of this study is to examine the effect of international financial reporting standard (IFRS) on the quality of financial statement (Using Sterling Bank as a case study). The specific objectives are to:

- i. examine the effect of IFRS on quality of financial statement in Nigeria.
- ii. examine whether the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) has improved the quality of financial reporting in Nigeria
- iii. examine the role IFRS play in Nigerian government financial statement

Literature Review

Internal Federal Revenue Services

The Nigeria's Federal Executive Council (FEC) gave approval for the convergence of Nigerian SAS with the IFRS from January 1, 2012. The adoption was organized such that all stakeholders use IFRS by January 2014. According to the IFRS adoption Roadmap Committee (2010), Public Listed Entities and Significant Public Interest Entities are expected to adopt the IFRS by January 2012. All Other Public Interest Entities are expected to mandatorily adopt the IFRS for statutory purposes by January 2013, and Small and Medium-sized Entities (SMEs) shall mandatorily adopt IFRS by January 2014. Nigerian listed entities were required to prepare their closing balances as at December 31, 2010 according to IFRS (Mechelli, Cimini & Mazzocchetti, 2017). The closing figures of December 31, 2010 will become the opening balances as at January 1, 2011 for IFRS based financial statements as at December 31, 2011. The opening balances for January 1, 2012 will be the first IFRS full financial statements prepared in accordance with the provision of IFRS as at December 31, 2012. "It will be in the interest of the Nigerian economy for listed companies to adopt globally accepted, high quality accounting standards, by fully

converging Nigerian National Accounting Standards with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) over the earliest possible transition period, given the increasing globalization of capital markets” (Ofoegbu & Odoemelum, 2018).

International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS)

IFRS are defined as Standards and Interpretations adopted by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB). International Financial reporting Standards comprises of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS); International Accounting Standards (IAS); interpretations originated by the International Financial Reporting Interpretations Committee (IFRIC) and Standing Interpretations Committee (SIC) (Olayinka , Paul & Olaoye, 2017). The International Accounting Standard Board (IASB) adopted International Accounting Standard (IASs) issued by the International Accounting Standard Committee (IASC) on 1 April, 2001 and the standards were adopted by over 90 countries around the world. International Accounting Standards includes IFRSs, IASs, SIC interpretations and IFRIC Interpretations. International Financial Reporting Standards are developed through an international process which includes accountants, financial analysts, stock exchanges, academics and other interested individuals, regulatory and legal authorities, business community, organizations around the world and other users of financial statement (Oroud, Islam, Ahmad & Ghazalat, 2019).

The International Accounting Standard Board (IASB) is funded and overseen by the International Accounting Standard Committee (IASC). The International Accounting Standard Board (IASB) also receives financial support from central and development banks, industrial companies throughout the world, accounting firms, international and professional organizations, major accounting firms and private financial institutions. International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) are body of prescriptive rules and guidelines with global reach and appeal which provide direction and guidance on how business enterprises in a globalised world could achieve the goal of proper record keeping, transparency, uniformity, comparability and enhancing public confidence in financial reporting (Ozili & Outa, 2019). Thus, failure on the part of the firm to apply the requirements of IFRS would result in inconsistencies, lack of accountability and transparency, distortion in financial reports, which in turn results into poor financial reporting practices and dissemination of accounting information that is of less value to any particular group of users. This is because the preparation and presentation of financial statements will be bereft of objectivity, reliability, credibility and comparability, and thus results in fraudulent business practices which subsequently lead to business failure and become devastating on the national economy (Suzuki & Takuma, 2017).

It is worthy of note that financial reporting pundits are unanimous in their agreement that financial reporting practice of a country depends on several factors that include the legal, economic, cultural and historical background of a country. It could then be argued that financial reporting is not an end in itself; rather, it is intended to provide information that is used in making reasoned choices among alternative uses of scarce resources in the conduct of business and economic activities. Therefore, this recognizes the fact that financial reports exist to satisfy the diverse information needs of numerous users such as the investors, management, employees, government, researchers, and so on. The problem is that firms have incentives to withhold or manipulate information in certain situations (poor performance) (Umoren, Akpan, & Ekeria, 2018).

This is because the publication of such information imposes both direct and indirect cost on the disclosing firm. Besides the cost of collating, processing, communicating and auditing the information to be published, the position of the disclosing firm may be damaged when such information is used by competitors, government agencies, trade unions, clients or suppliers. The importance of standardisation of accounting rule cannot be over accentuated (Uyar, Kılıç & Gökçen, 2017).

Theoretical Review

The New Institutional Theory is adopted as the theoretical background for this study. This theory has been widely used by various researchers in sociology, political science, business and management as well as information system and technology. The increasing use of institution theory in other research areas is also prevalent over the years. The corner stone year of the new institutional theory would have to be 1977 when John Meyer Published his paper "the effect of education as institution" in the American journal of sociology.

In the accounting research are, new institutional theory has been used to explain many case studies in management accounting, auditing, and institutional accounting. Accounting as one of the tools to produce information from the organization cannot be separated from the organization norms, value and behaviour. Many longitudinal case studies of management accounting use new institutional theory as a powerful tool to understand the behaviour of an organization over time. Not only in the micro level, but new institutional theory has also been used to explain the behaviour of a country or state in adopting accounting standards (Özcan, 2018).

In the context of IFRS convergence initiatives, institutionalization can be viewed as a social process through which a country accept that national accounting standards are absorbed in the interest of international accounting harmonization. In the field of international

accounting research, especially research on IFRS adoption/convergence, new institutional theory has been used both in quantitative and qualitative research. When a country decides to adopt IFRS and abandon their previous accounting standard, the main reason should be economical such as IFRS will bring economic benefit to the country. The economic benefit can be the decline in the cost of capital or the significant increase of foreign investors in the country's capital market. However, some studies suggest that the reason of a country adopting IFRS is not economical but more on achieving institutional legitimization (Birt, Joshi & Kend, 2017). Institutional theory has long been established as an important perspective in accounting research, because it provides insight into institutional dynamics in accounting. The usefulness of institutional theory has largely been driven by theoretical perspectives which broadly define accounting standards and practices as social institutions that are embedded in the institutional environment.

Review of Empirical Studies

Apochi & Mustapha (2022) assessed IFRS adoption and financial reporting quality in Nigeria with conceptual approach. The adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) in different countries of the world have become a contemporary issue particularly about the reliability of financial reports. The conceptual and empirical examination of the IFRS adoption and financial reporting quality across different sectors and countries. The study established that some studies used positive approach, and some used positive paradigm. Studies used either of primary or secondary source of data, while some used mixed approach. The study found that IFRS adoption are determined by comparing the parameters concerned between pre and post IFRS regimes in given jurisdictions. The review concept and empirical evidence of IFRS adoption and financial reporting quality from many countries reveals that economic consequences of IFRS adoption significantly differ across jurisdictions though its impact has been reported to be positive in majority of studies. Also, few studies report indifferent and negative effects of IFRS adoption on financial reporting quality. The study found that it is argued that IFRS is more financial position focused. It is also observed that the impact of mandatory adoption of IFRS tends to be greater disputed than that caused by voluntary IFRS adoption. In addition, IFRS adoption are found to supersede many other domestic financial reporting standards such as Statement of Accounting Standard (SAS) in Nigeria.

Mensah (2021) assessed the pre- and post-IFRS adoption effects on the financial reporting quality (FRQ) of manufacturing firms listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange (GSE) via means of correlation analysis, as well as regression analysis using a standard Fixed Effect (FE) model and the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique. Data was sourced from the

audited annual reports of eleven manufacturing firms observed over the period 2001 to 2006 for the pre-adoption era, and 2007 to 2014 for the post adoption era, making 148 firm-year observations. Using earnings management, measured by modified Jones' discretionary accruals, as a proxy for FRQ, the regression results showed a significant negative effect of IFRS adoption on earnings management, thus indicating an improvement in the FRQ. On the extent of earnings management practices both pre- and post-IFRS adoption, the study finds a decrease in the post-adoption era as against the pre-adoption era, also signifying an improvement in accounting quality after the adoption of IFRS. The findings of this study indicate that, IFRS adoption enhances the quality of firms' financial reports within the Ghanaian capital market, which is envisaged to boost investor confidence and attract more capital.

Umoren, Uyar and Sunder (2020) examined the effect of IFRS adoption on the quality of financial statements of selected firms on the Ghana Stock Exchange. The study used the extent of management practices as a metric for financial statement quality. The audited annual reports of the selected firms from the GSE were analyzed using a panel regression model over the period 2001-2006 and 2007-2014. The study finds the adoption of IFRS to be significantly and negatively affect earnings management practices and, thus, improves financial statement quality. On the extent of earnings management practices, the study finds a decrease in the postadoption era as opposed to the preadoption era, signifying an improvement in accounting quality. The panel regression results show that adopting IFRS significantly decreases the extent of earnings management.

Ezeagba (2017) examined the impact of International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) adoption on the financial reporting practice of selected commercial banks in Nigerian using some financial ratios selected from three major categories of financial ratios. The population comprise of 21 commercial banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) as at December 31, 2014. Eleven banks were selected based on availability of data required for the investigation. This study was conducted through the comparison of ratios that were computed from IFRS based financial statements and Nigerian GAAP based financial statements. The Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test was used to test whether significant difference exists in the profitability, liquidity and leverage of banks using IFRS and Nigerian GAAP financial statements. We therefore recommended that there should also be much more enlightenment campaigns on the potential effects of IFRS implementation by the regulatory authorities, professional bodies and government before the impact in Nigeria gets worsened and out of hand. Furthermore, companies should endeavour to use the opportunity presented by the adoption of IFRS to improve their business processes in all ramifications so as to aid uniformity and transparency.

Taiwo and Adejare (2014) empirically analysed the effect of international financial reporting standards (IFRS) adoption on accounting practices in Nigeria. The study adopted personal interview and questionnaire methods* * as the major techniques for primary data collection. Data collected were analyzed using both descriptive such as tables, frequencies and percentages and inferential statistics of Chi-square and ANOVA respectively. The study concluded that that there is a strong positive relationship between the adoption of IFRS and financial performance due to cost reduction of an organisation. IFRS adoption improves business efficiency and productivity for effective business performance. The adoption of IFRS saves Multinational Corporations the expense of preparing more than one set of accounts for different national jurisdictions. It is recommended that the financial reporting practice in Nigeria should cut across the public and private sector to bring uniformity in accounting practice regarding annual preparation of financial reports to the owner of companies and other interested parties.

Okpala (2012) studies adoption of IFRS and financial statements effects, the perceived implications on FDI and Nigeria economy. The IFRS adoption is already an issue of global relevance among various countries of the world due to the quest for uniformity, reliability, and comparability of financial statements of companies. This research paper investigated the effect of IFRS adoption on Foreign Direct Investment and Nigeria economy. The population consists of quoted companies in Nigeria Stock Exchange (Preparers) and Investment Analysts (Users). Stratified Random sampling method was adopted, and primary data used to elicit responses with 123 structured questionnaires administered. Findings showed that IFRS has been adopted in Nigeria but only fraction of companies has implemented with deadline for the others to comply. It is perceived that IFRS implementation will promote FDI inflows and economic growth. It was recommended that all stakeholders should endeavour to have full implementation to reap benefits of the global GAAP and principle - based standards.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population is represented by 150 members of staff of Sterling Bank in Ibadan, Oyo State. Sixty (60) staff were randomly selected and questionnaire were administered to them. The questionnaire adopted the 4-point Likert type summation scale weight. The method of data analysis used for this study was Statistical analysis for Social Sciences (SPSS) as well as descriptive statistical method were tables and simple percentages will be used to analyse the information in the questionnaire supplied so as to allow accuracy and easy decoding of information.

Results and Presentation of Data

Table 1: Analysis of Demographic Data of Respondents

Variables	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	13	26
	Female	37	74
	Total	50	100.0
Educational Qualification	ND/NCE	13	26
	B.Sc./HND	30	60
	PhD	5	19
	Professional	2	4
	Total	50	100.0
Marital Status	Single	35	70
	Married	15	30
	Total	50	100.0
Age distribution	24-30 years	30	60
	31-40 years	12	24
	41-50 years	5	10
	57 years and above	3	6
	Total	50	100.0
Designation	Supervisory	10	20
	Managerial	6	9
	Total	50	100.0
	Others	34	71

The table above reveals that majority of respondents are female with 74%(37) while male is 13%(26). This shows that the majority of workers of Sterling Bank Plc, Ibadan Oyo State, are female. The table also shows that 31%(11) respondents had ND/NCE; B.Sc/ HND had 49%(17) PhD had 14%(5) and 6%(2) were professionals. This statistics reveal that above 80% of the employees had either ND, B.Sc or HND qualification, few had PhD or were professionals.

The analysis above shows that the majority of respondents fall into the single category 35% (70), while the married is 15 % (30). This implies that the majority of employees are single. The table above shows the age distribution of the respondents. Employees of 24-30 years had 60 % (30); 31-40 years. had 24%(12); 41-50 10% (5) and 51 years and above had 6% (3). This reveals that the majority of employees at Sterling Bank Plc, Ibadan Oyo State are between the age range to 24 to 30 years. The table shows the respondents according to designation. Those on supervisory level were 20%(10); those on managerial level were 9%(6) and others were 71%(34). This reveals that the majority of employees in Sterling Bank Plc, Ibadan Oyo State, fall into Other Category which is 71%(34).

Data Analysis

Table 2: Does International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) aid quality of financial statement in Nigeria?

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Comparability Index of Assets	14	.9854	.03471	.00928

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Interpretation

The mean comparability index of 0.9854 in table 2 above suggests that total assets under (International Accounting Standards/International Financial Reporting Standards) IAS/IFRS are greater than that of Nigerian **Generally Accepted Accounting Principles** (GAAP) for all the sampled six banks, with the level of clustering of individual bank's assets closer to the mean of all the six sampled banks' assets. This contrasts to that of total liabilities and total equities. This picture is as depicted by the standard deviation and standard error of mean of 0.03471 and 0.00928 respectively.

Table 3: Does International Financial Reporting Standards play any significant role in Nigerian Government financial statement?

	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Comparability Index of Assets	106.215	13	.000	.98538	.9653	1.0054

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Interpretation

From table 3 above, it could be inferred that the asymptotic significance of 0.000 is less than the level of significance employed in this study. Consequently, the null hypothesis that the quantitative differences in the financial reports (total assets) prepared under Nigerian Generally Accepted Accounting Principles and International Accounting Standards/International Financial Reporting Standards are not statistically significant stands rejected while the alternative hypothesis that the quantitative differences in the financial reports prepared under Nigerian Generally Accepted Accounting Principles and International Accounting Standards/International Financial Reporting Standards are statistically significant stands accepted.

Table 4: Is there any problem confronting the Nigerian government in enhancing quality financial statement?

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Comparability Index of Liabilities	14	.9831	.04307	.01151

(Source: SPSS Output, 2022)

Interpretation

The mean comparability index of 0.9831 in table 4 above suggests that total assets under International Accounting Standards/International Financial Reporting Standards are greater than that of Nigerian Generally Accepted Accounting Principles for all the sampled fourteen banks. The comparability indices of individual bank's liabilities disperse more around the total mean liabilities, compared to that of assets. This picture is as depicted by the standard deviation and standard error of mean of 0.04307 and 0.01151 respectively.

Discussions of the Findings

Having given a careful analysis of the responses obtained from the respondents through questionnaire administered, the hypothesis formulated were tested, and in doing so, Statistical analysis for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to performed statistical analysis in testing the various hypotheses through the chi square and with a value of 5 percent (level of significance) that corresponds to a 95 percent confidence level. Therefore, the tables presented above are SPSS outputs it means that the independent variable (IFRS adoption) has an influence on the dependent variable (Clarity), As such, we reject the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between IFRS adoption and the clarity principle of Nigerian banks and accept the alternate hypothesis, which states that there is a significant relationship between IFRS adoption and the clarity principle of Nigerian banks. The essential qualities of information in financial reports. Achieving this is through effective communication the better the understanding by users, the higher the quality that will be achieved. When annual reports are well organized users can comprehend what their needs are.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examines the effect of international financial reporting standard (IFRS) on the quality of financial statement (Using Sterling Bank as a case study). From the result, the major benefits derivable from the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards include imposition of a more comprehensive and highly detailed set of disclosure requirements than domestic accounting standards; constrain managerial discretion, improvement in accounting quality, which in turn contributes to a generally transparent firm information environment and better accounting practice. Improved comparability is also one of the value-adding characteristics of International Financial Reporting Standards as contended by most financial reporting pundits, as it will make it less costly for investors to compare and evaluate firms inside and outside industries and countries.

Financial reporting is shaped by incentives.

However, the study offers the following recommendations:

1. Companies should prepare adequately on all fronts for the implementation of IFRS.
2. Companies should endeavour to use the opportunity presented by the adoption of IFRS to improve their business process and procedures.
3. Companies that are required to adopt IFRS should also be involved in capacity building by organizing conferences and seminars for members and staff of the company on IFRS.
4. Nigeria's adoption of IFRS should be supported as a matter of urgency to enable full attainment of the country's economic potential.
5. As the timetable for the adoption of IFRS in Nigeria has been determined, the need to properly re-evaluate the activities of the major institutions connected with the implementation of the new standard should be urgently considered.
6. IFRS should be included in the syllabus of Accounting Department in the tertiary institutions so that students will have the knowledge before entering into the labour market.
7. The accounting education curricula in Nigeria's tertiary institutions and secondary schools should urgently be reviewed to reflect current realities and actual business practices and for that purpose should capture an adequate dose: provisions and thrust of IFRS of their output are to remain globally competitive.
8. The accountancy institutes in Nigeria must embark on massive education training and retraining of their members through continuing professional development programmes.
9. The education, sensitisation and communication to shareholders of issues associated with IFRS vis-à-vis the role of the relevant institution should commence in earnest. Also,
10. There is need to strengthen the financial reporting institutional framework by further empowering the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria.

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